

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: LEUZZI****FIRST NAME: EMMARYN****PROGRAM CODE : DSDD****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: ONE****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics (only keep US or UK)

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did *not* use Zotero to insert references (remove unneeded text to indicate)

The author did not use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID) (remove unneeded text)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: xx%

The author used the following software: MSWord 2016 on Windows 11 Pro

List your 7 key concepts with page number in text (then bold these terms in your RP)(samples below):

1. Introduction to academic writing (EUCLID 2024, 1-16)
2. Scholarly writing-an overview (EUCLID, 2024)
3. Fundamentals of scholarly writing (EUCLID 2024, 16-22)
4. Punctuation marks (EUCLID 2024, 40)
5. Plagiarism (EUCLID 2024, 51-55)
6. British vs American English (EUCLID 2024, 61-64)
7. Latin expressions and abbreviations (EUCLID 2024, 73)

SCHOLARLY WRITING-AN OVERVIEW

1) INTRODUCTION

In recent times, many have been liberated to write as and when, to opine without reverence to the scope of language nor guided by the rules of writing. Once a point has been made, regardless of whether or not certain words ought to be in the written piece, it is the least of concern to the non-academic writer. It is quite common to read and hear individuals- for example- in the same sentence use American and British words to argue or make a statement. ‘I normally keep a pair pants in the car boot on a rainy day’-this statement is technically incorrect, given that both the US and UK conventions of grammar were utilized by the speaker in the same sentence.

What distinguishes scholars from other writers is the articulate ‘obedience’ to standards. The art of writing is but a gift if one adheres to the set principles. Not only do scholarly works exude facts, but the tone of adherence also sets the mark. This piece will delve into the set principles of scholarly writing or academic writing. These two terms will be used interchangeably. Academic writing is “nonfictional writing produced as part of academic work” (EUCLID 2024, 5).

2) FUNDAMENTALS OF SCHOLARLY WRITING

As with any other project, be it construction or cuisine, the quality of scholarly writing depends on the organization of thoughts. This serves as the very building block of any writing. A well-organized pool of ideas goes a long way to engaging readers to easily comprehend your purpose of writing.

Firstly, the topic of interest must be thoroughly researched to understand the stance of the writer. There are tons of information easily accessible when embarking on writing on certain topics, whereas other topics have yet to be explored. Careful scrutiny of topics enables you to stick to a defined trajectory, which further leads to organizing your ideas.

The development of ideas after researching leads to the construction of a literary piece. Scholarly writing is partitioned into three main parts: the isolation of either becomes a train without an engine or without a railway. The introduction, the body, and the conclusion are the major components of academic writing.

The introduction, as the word depicts, is synonymous with the trailer of a movie to the audience. It gives a general overview of what readers are expected to read or understand from the writing. The overview is the preceding piece, which highlights the topic, the chapters, nuances, and rhetoric projected in the piece. The body serves as the main component in scholarly writing; it comprises of developed ideas, opinions, further digestion of the topic, and possesses answers to questions. A well-written body further enlightens the reader to the extent of opining similarly to the writer. The conclusion is the summary of all arguments sustained in the body, readdresses the introduction, and captures all salient information. In writing the conclusion of a scholarly work, it is worth noting that, although it contains future projects of the written ideas, the conclusion must not introduce a new topic (EUCLID 2024, 10).

a) **Dotting the ‘i’s and crossing the ‘t’s**

Punctuations are synonymous with the accessories of a garment in writing, without which the logical flow of a paper is inhibited. As the full stop ends a sentence or an idea, commas, brackets, apostrophes, colons, and all other punctuation marks play a significant role in the expression of an idea. Regardless of how minute they seem, punctuation marks can totally change an idea of a sentence. The following examples will demonstrate the essence of adding commas in sentences when needed and, more so, correctly applying them;

1) I like cooking my family and my pets.

2) A woman, without her man, is nothing.

A woman; without her, man is nothing.

The first sentence without punctuation creates the impression that the writer is involved in a sort of crime - killing, and cooking of their relatives and pets! Ignoring the use of commas, in this case, changes the entire purpose of this statement, where the writer only wanted to state things that they enjoyed doing.

The next sentence above clearly demonstrates how little commas send a powerful statement. The first part depicts the argument of the vulnerability of a woman without a male partner. The latter, with a different positioning of the punctuation marks, strongly expresses the exact opposite of the preceding sentence.

Other rules to be observed when using punctuation marks, as opined by Cleenewerck and Gulma (2024, 19), include not using a comma where defining information starts a sentence, avoiding the use of a comma in a time-based adverbial phrase. Other regulations to abide by in the world of punctuation are the use of the dash, that is, using the n-dash in place of a colon and in place of commas and round brackets where words or ideas are surrounded by spaces. The n-dash is also used to link concepts and express a range of numbers, for example, '*my salary expectation ranges from \$2000-\$4000 per month.*' It is also used for joint names of similar contexts '*The Biden-Harris administration vows to end gun violence in its era*'. On the other hand, the hyphen is not to be used in noun phrases to make a new compound noun if it is a recognizable concept (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 21).

b) Copy Cat, Copy and Tell...

Plagiarism is the greatest 'crime' that could ever be committed in academia; in academia, regurgitated ideas should always be acknowledged. This seems like a very basic rule to adhere to by scholars. Nevertheless, it is the easiest rule to break. Acknowledging one's work in yours is very crucial. Trouble starts when there is paraphrasing or a seemingly total change of the author's written statement. Paraphrasing and rephrasing easily fall into the net of plagiarism. Many novice writers like me are torn between citing an author when there is rephrasing of ideas or applying general common knowledge. The course pack provides the foundations for understanding and avoiding plagiarism.

In plain language, plagiarism is the failure to mention the source of a copied idea, statistic, or data and/or presenting another author's work as yours. Avoiding this is by always stating the source of a reproduced idea or data (ibid. 34). Plagiarism, when exposed, may have dire consequences on the offender, such as a stained unethical reputation and withdrawal of any award or benefit the plagiarized material offered among others. Citing sources in writing can take different forms, such as having an in-text citation or simply listing the resources used in presenting your ideas.

In-text citations are used when quotations and paraphrases are employed in writing. When an idea or statement of another author is directly lifted in your piece, that is, in quotation marks- the author and year of publication (depending on the style guide) is mentioned in parentheses. Similarly, paraphrasing occurs when you rewrite another author's ideas in your own words (EUCLID 2024, 36). This style also demands the use of

in-text citations. However, it is worth noting that not all ideas or facts need to be cited; general knowledge and repeated ideas in several sources. Also, it is important to cite your previous works if they have been used in new writing; failure to do so leads to self-plagiarism. It is unethical to present a previous finding of yours as though it were new. Other methods of avoiding plagiarism include the use of footnotes, bibliography, and referencing.

i) *British vs American English*

British and American English, both largely used, have dissections and intersections in the scope of language. This section will delve into different words used to express the same meaning, different pronunciations with the same spelling, different spelling but with the same pronunciations, same term- different but similar spelling with different pronunciation, and finally, same words with different or additional meanings. (EUCLID 2024, 26).

In British English, the storage compartment of a vehicle, which is usually positioned at the back, is referred to as the ‘car boot’, whereas in American English, it is referred to as the ‘trunk’. Another example of different words used to express the same meaning is the use of ‘sidewalk’ in American English in place of the British ‘pavement’ for pedestrians. Flats, trousers, aubergine, and underground are all American equivalents of apartment, pants, eggplant, and subway, respectively.

Interestingly, both languages intersect by having the same spellings but with different pronunciations such as advertisement, finance, schedule, and dynasty (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024,25). Contrastingly, there are different spellings with the same pronunciations such as; cheque (British English) for a check, axe (British English) for ax, and paediatrician (British) for pediatrician (American).

Illustrations of the same term with different but similar spelling and pronunciation can be seen in these sets of words: aluminium (British), aluminum (American); maths (British), and math (American). Finally, words such as ‘bomb’ in American English could also mean ‘terrific’ in British English (aside from the primary meaning of the word to mean a type of arsenal), and this falls under the category of the same words but with different or additional meanings.

A careful study of these variations guides writers to stick to either one of them depending on their [cultural] history, geographic background, or simply their audience. Mixing both British and American English in academic writing is a faux pas.

ii) *Latin expressions and abbreviations*

Latin expressions serve as the mother tongue of most modern languages and are usually used as technical terminologies in professional fields such as law and philosophy. The good news is, that most of these expressions have found their way in plain language, thus, it does not become a headache for the modern English speaker to remember and correctly pronounce.

Nonetheless, certain expressions have come to stay and are more often used in writing than their plain English equivalents. For *e.g., et cetera, lpm, 12am*, among others, are quite popular terms. These expressions are even more grounded in writing and speech with their abbreviations.

‘Latin abbreviations are appropriate in footnotes, bibliographies, and informal writing (e.g., the information in parentheses)’ (ibid, 59). English equivalents are more appropriate to use in business and publicity to avoid misinterpretation and confusion among readers.

3) CONCLUSION

Scholarly writing abides by several regulations that contribute to its overall quality. It is not just enough to put together facts and findings; logical flow, punctuations, abbreviations, language, referencing, and overall style guide is what sets scholars apart. This paper has highlighted key considerations for putting together facts and opinions in academia. These include the basic rules of academic writing as seen above in fundamentals of scholarly writing, the proper use of punctuation marks, avoiding plagiarism, making a choice between British and Academic English, and finally, the use of Latin abbreviations and expressions.

REFERENCES

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